

Sociological perspective

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Introduction

A perspective can be defined as a way of seeing and being seen anything. Therefore having a perspective means looking something in a particular way. For sociologists, the thing that is observed is the social world, that is, the different ways in which humans behave socially. So when there is talk about "society" or the social world that to which people really refer to is the behavior of human beings, the real target of study for sociologists. In this topic, the main purpose is to observe and detect different actions of a human being. The location that has been selected to observe is Wal-Mart stores. The duration of the observation is going to be just 25 minutes that is not very long but it will help in having a good idea related to the activities taking place in the Wal-Mart stores. Therefore, all the aspects in this regard will be discussed in detail.

Discussion

The importance of the sociological perspective in the social world is very high. The main reason is that it helps in having a perspective that also explains a specific theory which certainly proves to be useful in gaining an understanding about an issue. Sociological perspective is formed by a sub-set of different perspectives. Still, it is possible to identify a few common ideas on which most sociologists, if not all agree. The human social behavior is learned, not instinctive. In this respect, the explanation is that people need to learn, give the time of the birth, as being not only a human being, but also to be an identifiable member of the society into which people are born. For that to understand human social behavior people have focused their attention on the groups to which people belong. These groups are many and varied, as people

shall see, but the largest group they belong to people is society. Sociology is a perspective that looks at the totality of relationships. In this sense, sociologists do not restrict their look (study) to a single dimension of social activity (Economics, Politics, History, Geography, Psychology, etc.). Although each of these disciplines is important and interesting, just studying how these relationships affect on each other, people can get a complete picture of human social behavior. This final idea brings people to briefly consider other, possibly complementary social sciences. Sociologists do not reject the contributions of researchers in other areas such as economics, politics or psychology. At the same time, the existence of sociology as an academic discipline is based on the recognition that human beings are not one-dimensional but multidimensional beings. Many times, explanations of sociologists differ from the interpretations of "common sense" that usually occur on human behavior (Dant, 2013).

In the case of making an observation during the visit to the Wal-Mart stores, there are several areas that can be noticed. The main observation is related to the shopping activity that is going to take place in the Wal-mart stores. In fact, it is the main activity that is going to be observed but the sociological perspective will main focus on the human behavior. This will include such as the types of people doing shopping in the Wal-Mart stores. There are going to be different segments of the people such as families, couples, relatives, friends etc. The social behavior of these people will be very much different as their interaction will vary considerably. This is a typical feature for any supermarket. It will thus be observed that what type of communication pattern is taking place among different people. The cultural values of the people will even reflect during such a case as there are going to be Americans belonging to different backgrounds such as Asian Americans, Arab Americans, Hispanics etc. This will further add a

lot of variety while observing people. This is the main feature of the sociological perspective that is commonly noted for any physical place (Meyer, 2010).

The sociological perspective allows people to better understand the opportunities and obstacles that will be encountered in lives. Sociology shows people that the company operates with certain rules. It helps people understand what those rules and how they apply. Sociology can help people understand what are the difficulties that they may find trying to accomplish the goals and to better refine these goals and be more effective when it comes to achieving them. Sociology is part of the ever-changing world. Companies are constantly changing. There are fixed objects, and change as the sociologist studying. People have to wait for the knowledge of society change too quickly. Sociologists are members of a society that are part of the object of study. The sociological knowledge ends up being part of society. Research and studies that sociologists who write books, the explanations offered on many different things, end up being part of the knowledge that a society has of itself. Sociologists suggest ideas that can become applied; reaching converted into part of a society. This is the reason why sociological perspective carries immense importance for any society (Hatch, 2012).

Conclusion

In the end, it can be said that the sociological perspective followed during the observation of the activities taking place in Wal-mart stores carried immense importance. There were many human behaviors which were observed that helped in gaining a detailed sociological insight of shopping activity. Therefore, all the aspects related to Sociological perspective have been discussed in detail.

References

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